

Facile synthesis of a novel tetrazole Schiff base complex of Co^{III} via [3+2] cycloaddition of metal coordinated azide with cyanopyridine

Mithun Das and Shouvik Chattopadhyay*

Department of Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry Section, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail : shouvik.chem@gmail.com

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Abstract : The 1 : 2 condensation of ethylenediamine and salicylaldehyde yields a tetradentate N₂O₂ ligand *N,N'*-bis-salicylidene-1,2-ethylenediimine (H₂L = H₂Salen). When cobalt(II) acetate is added to the methanolic solution of H₂L, followed by addition of sodium azide, a cobalt(III) azido Schiff base compound, Co₂L₂(N₃)₂ is formed. When this compound was made to react with 2-cyanopyridine under stirring condition, a novel cobalt(III) compound containing azide, tetrazole and Salen, [Co(H₂CN₄)L(N₃)] (**1**), was produced. The compound was characterized by C, H, N analysis, UV-Vis, IR and X-ray crystal diffraction study.

Keywords : Cobalt(III), tetrazole, H₂Salen, crystal structure, cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

Tetrazoles have been studied for more than hundred years and have found a wide range of applications in coordination chemistry as ligands with various coordination modes¹, in medicinal chemistry as a metabolically stable surrogate for a carboxylic acid group² and in material science as high density energy materials³⁻⁶. The most widely used synthetic route to obtain tetrazoles was via [3+2] cycloaddition of sodium azide with a nitrile⁷. Synthesis by this traditional method showed various drawbacks such as long reaction times and high temperature etc. The use of water as a solvent and zinc salts as catalyst was shown to overcome these drawbacks by providing a convenient and environment-friendly synthetic route to tetrazoles in high yields at moderate temperature with a low reaction time⁸. It is worth mentioning here that the construction and application of tetrazoles as ligands by single-pot *in situ* hydrothermal reactions in the presence of various transition metals have also been studied⁹⁻¹². However, reports on the synthesis of tetrazoles using cycloaddition reactions under mild and controlled conditions with first row transition metals are scanty¹³⁻¹⁵. Recently, works on metal mediated cycloaddition reactions between organonitriles and metal coordinated azide (other than sodium azide itself) have contributed a lot to the synthesis of novel tetrazole complexes, preferably

under mild conditions¹⁶⁻²⁰. Keeping this in mind, we planned to study the cycloaddition reactions of 2-cyanopyridine with the azide activated by a metal centre bearing salen as a ligand.

It is well known that the low-spin t_{2g}^6 configuration of cobalt(III) is inert towards any kind of substitution reaction. Therefore, we select cobalt(III) as the metal centre where azide is coordinated so that the prepared tetrazole would remain bonded to the metal centre. The well known Schiff base, 1,6-bis(2-hydroxyphenyl)-2,5-diazahexa-1,5-diene (commonly known as H₂Salen, general abbreviation H₂L, where H atoms are dissociable phenolic hydrogen atoms) has been used as a tetradentate chelating ligand in the present work. The reaction of H₂L with cobalt(II) acetate in presence of NaN₃ furnished a binuclear cobalt(III) compound [CoL(N₃)₂]²¹. Interestingly when this compound was made to react with 2-cyanopyridine, an unexpected tetrazole cobalt(III) compound [Co(H₂CN₄)L(N₃)] (**1**) is produced (Scheme 1). In the present paper, we report the synthesis, spectroscopic characterizations, crystal structure and redox behavior of the novel tetrazole Schiff base compound of cobalt(III).

The compound **1** has been synthesized by reaction of compound [CoL(N₃)₂] with 2-cyanopyridine at ambient temperature²² (Scheme 1). Single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction analysis were obtained on overnight stand-

Scheme 1. Routine procedure for the synthesis of compound **1**.

ing in fridge²³. The ligand (H_2L) was prepared by the 1 : 2 condensation of the ethylenediamine with salicylaldehyde in methanol following the literature method²⁴. The ligand was then refluxed with a mixture of cobalt(II) acetate and sodium azide to prepare the desired oxo-bridged dimeric cobalt(III) compound $[\text{CoL(N}_3)_2]$ ²¹. This compound was then made to react with 2-cyanopyridine under stirring condition to convert the azide into 2-pyridyl tetrazolate via [3+2] cycloaddition. Surprisingly, the isolated complex does not contain 2-pyridyl tetrazolate, instead the cobalt(III) is coordinated by an unsubstituted tetrazole unit. This can be explained if we assume that the tetrazole is eliminated from the 2 position of the pyridine moiety of 2-pyridyl tetrazole, which was formed as the intermediate. It is also well known that 2 (and 6) position(s) of pyridine is susceptible to nucleophilic substitution. We assume that after the formation of 2-pyridyl tetrazole, it is attacked by any nucleophile present in the medium and as a result, free tetrazole is formed, which, in turn, coordinates the cobalt(III) centre to form compound **1**. Alternatively, 2-pyridyl tetrazole may coordinate the cobalt(III) first, followed by the elimination of pyridine.

Elemental analysis (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) was performed using a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. IR spectra in KBr ($4500\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer RXI FT-IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra in DMF ($1200\text{--}350\text{ nm}$) were recorded in a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were done with an EG & PAR vibrating sample magnetometer, model 155 at room temperature and diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants. Electrochemical measurements were performed in DMF solution under a dry nitrogen atmosphere in conventional three-electrode configurations using a Pt disk working electrode, Pt auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode, with tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate as supporting electrolyte in the potential range from -2 to 2 V , and were uncorrected for junction contribution. The value for the Fc-Fc^+ couple under our conditions is 0.39 V .

In the IR spectrum, distinct band due to the azomethine (C=N) group at 1634 cm^{-1} is customarily noticed²⁵. The sharp, strong, single peak at 2023 cm^{-1} gives evidence for the presence of monodentate azide²⁶. The electronic spectrum in DMF solution exhibits an absorption at 503

nm, attributable to a transition of a low-spin cobalt(III) in octahedral geometry. The high-energy, intense band at 388 nm is associated with a charge-transfer transition²⁷.

The perspective view of compound **1** is shown in Fig. 1. The asymmetric unit is composed of four molecules of **1**. Selected bond distances and bond angles are given in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively. Each molecule has a

N(2)] and two phenoxy O-atoms [O(1) and O(2)] of L²⁻ and the remaining two axial sites were occupied by two N-atoms [N(3) and N(7)] of tetrazole and terminal azide respectively. Interestingly, in the present compound, sp² hybridised tetrazolyl N-atom is coordinated to cobalt(III) avoiding the most common coordination pattern through the sp³ hybridised N-atom. This causes a unique coor-

Fig. 1. The perspective view of the compound **1** with selective atom numbering scheme.

cobalt(III), which is coordinated to a deprotonated tetradentated N₂O₂ donor Schiff base (L²⁻), a tetrazole and a terminal azide. The coordination geometry around cobalt(III) is octahedral, where four equatorial coordinate site was occupied by two azomethine N-atoms [N(1) and

Table 1. Selective bond lengths around cobalt(III) of compound **1**

Co(1)–N(1)	1.90(3)	Co(3)–N(19)	1.89(2)
Co(1)–N(2)	1.88(3)	Co(3)–N(20)	1.88(3)
Co(1)–N(3)	1.99(2)	Co(3)–N(21)	1.95(2)
Co(1)–N(7)	1.92(2)	Co(3)–N(25)	1.94(3)
Co(1)–O(1)	1.89(2)	Co(3)–O(5)	1.88(2)
Co(1)–O(2)	1.91(2)	Co(3)–O(6)	1.86(2)
Co(2)–N(10)	1.89(3)	Co(4)–N(28)	1.89(3)
Co(2)–N(11)	1.85(3)	Co(4)–N(29)	1.87(3)
Co(2)–N(12)	1.96(2)	Co(4)–N(30)	1.99(2)
Co(2)–N(16)	1.93(2)	Co(4)–N(34)	1.95(2)
Co(2)–O(3)	1.88(2)	Co(4)–O(7)	1.89(2)
Co(2)–O(4)	1.90(2)	Co(4)–O(8)	1.89(2)

Table 2. Selected bond angles around cobalt(III) of the compound **1**

N(1)–Co(1)–N(2)	80.81(2)
N(1)–Co(1)–N(3)	95.96(2)
N(1)–Co(1)–N(4)	177.28(2)
N(1)–Co(1)–N(5)	90.47(2)
N(1)–Co(1)–N(8)	89.91(2)
N(2)–Co(1)–N(3)	85.79(2)
N(2)–Co(1)–N(4)	97.76(2)
N(2)–Co(1)–N(5)	170.49(2)
N(2)–Co(1)–N(8)	90.0(2)
N(3)–Co(1)–N(4)	81.60(2)
N(3)–Co(1)–N(5)	91.39(2)
N(3)–Co(1)–N(8)	172.15(2)
N(4)–Co(1)–N(5)	90.80(2)
N(4)–Co(1)–N(8)	92.41(2)
N(5)–Co(1)–N(8)	93.8(2)
Co(1)–N(5)–N(6)	121.6(4)
Co(1)–N(8)–N(9)	122.7(4)

dination of a neutral tetrazole with the metal.

The saturated five membered ring [Co(1)–N(1)–C(8)–C(9)–N(2)] has an half-chair conformation twisted on C(8)–C(9) with puckering parameters $Q(2) = 0.32(3)$ Å and $\phi(2) = 277(4)$ °. The N(1)–Co(1)–N(2) angle is $87.4(12)$ ° and is typical of a five-membered chelate ring²⁹. In the octahedral complex of a Salen-type ligand, when it acts as a tetradentate ligand, two different arrangements of four donor atoms around the metal atom is found; one in which the donors occupy the four equatorial positions, the other in which one oxygen is displaced from the equatorial plane, occupying an axial position of the coordination polyhedron³⁰. In the present case, the ligand necessarily assumes the first alternative.

Electrochemical measurement was performed in DMF solution under a dry nitrogen atmosphere in conventional three electrode configurations using Pt disk working electrode, Pt auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode, with TBAP (Tetrabutylammonium perchlorate) as supporting electrolyte in the potential range from –2 V to 2 V and were uncorrected for junction contribution. The value for the Fc–Fc⁺ couple under our conditions is 0.39 V.

A scan initiated in the negative direction at 0.0 V reveals a first irreversible reduction wave at –0.28 V due to cobalt(III)/cobalt(II) reduction. A second, well-defined quasi-reversible process at –0.84 V is observed corresponding to the simple one-electron process of cobalt(II)/cobalt(I) reduction. The criteria of reversibility was checked by observing constancy of peak-peak separation ($\Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$) and the ratio of peak heights ($i_{pa}/i_{pc} \sim 1$) with variation of scan rates³¹. The single-electron nature of the voltammogram has been confirmed by the comparison of current height for the compound and that of a simple [Fe(bipy)₃]²⁺ compound under identical conditions³². Upon reversal of the scan direction, the cobalt(II) complex is reoxidized to cobalt(III) at higher potentials at 0.98 V. The electrochemical data are given in Table 3.

The results of cyclic voltammetry also closely resemble that of the similar reported compounds, which serve as further evidences for similar structural and electronic properties^{27,33}. All the redox signals remain virtually invariant under different scan rates (0.01–1.0 V s^{–1}) in the temperature range 300–280 K. Solvent dependent shift and change in electrochemical reversibility of redox couples are not noteworthy.

The Hirshfeld surfaces of the compounds are illustrated in Fig. 2, showing surfaces that have been mapped over a d_{norm} (range of –0.5 to 1.5 Å), shape index and curvedness³⁴. The surfaces are shown as transparent to allow visualization of the molecular moiety, in a similar orientation for d_{norm} , shape index and curvedness, around which they were calculated.

The dominant interactions between N...H and C...H atoms in the compound **1** can be seen in the Hirshfeld surface as the red areas in Fig. 2. Other visible spots in the Hirshfeld surfaces correspond to H...H contacts. The small extent of area and light color on the surface indicates weaker and longer contact. The N...H/H...N intermolecular interactions appear as distinct spikes in the 2D fingerprint plot (Fig. 2f). Complementary regions are visible in the fingerprint plots where one molecule act as donor ($d_e > d_i$) and the other as an acceptor ($d_e < d_i$). The fingerprint plots can be decomposed to highlight particular atoms pair close contacts³⁵. This decomposition enables separation of contributions from different interaction types, which overlap in the full fingerprint. The amount of N...H/H...N interactions comprises 27.10% of the Hirshfeld surfaces for each molecule of compound **1**. The N...H interactions are represented by a spike ($d_i = 1.372$, $d_e = 0.931$ Å) in the bottom left (donor) area of the fingerprint plot (Fig. 2), indicating H-atoms of Schiff bases of one molecule are interacting with N-atom of the azide and tetrazole of other molecule (Fig. 2d). The H...N interactions are represented by another spike ($d_i = 0.931$, $d_e = 1.367$ Å) in the bottom right (acceptor) region of fingerprint plot, where azide nitrogen also

Table 3. Electrochemical data for the oxidation and reduction of the cobalt(III) centre of the compound **1**

Compd.	E_{pc} (III → II) (V)	$\text{Co}^{\text{II}}/\text{Co}^{\text{I}}$				E_{pa} (II → III) (V)
		E_{pa} (V)	E_{pc} (V)	$E_{1/2}$ (V)	ΔE_p (mV)	
1	–0.28	–0.55	–1.13	0.84	580	0.98

$E_{1/2}$ is calculated as the average of anodic (E_{pa}) and cathodic (E_{pc}) peak potentials; $\Delta E_p = (E_{pa} - E_{pc})$.

Fig. 2. Hirshfeld surface mapped over d_{norm} (a), shape index (b) and curvedness (c) for compounds **1** and fingerprint plots of **1** : Full (f) and resolved into N \cdots H/H \cdots N (d) and C \cdots H/H \cdots C (e) contacts showing the percentages of contacts contributed to the total Hirshfeld surface area of molecules.

acts as acceptor to the H atoms of Schiff bases of other molecules and these nitrogen-based interactions represent the closest contacts in the structures and can be viewed as a pair of large red spots on the d_{norm} surface (Fig. 2d). Similarly the amount of C \cdots H/H \cdots C interactions comprises 24.5% of the Hirshfeld surfaces for each molecule. The C \cdots H interactions are represented by a spike ($d_i = 1.492$, $d_e = 0.991$ Å) in the bottom left (donor) area of the fingerprint plot (Fig. 2e), indicating that Schiff base H-atoms interacting with C-atoms of the Schiff base of other molecules. The H \cdots C interactions are represented by another spike ($d_i = 0.991$, $d_e = 1.477$ Å) in the bottom right (acceptor) region of fingerprint plot (Fig. 2e), where Schiff base C-atoms also act as acceptor to the H atoms of the other Schiff bases.

The report provides the first synthetic route for tetrazole complex of cobalt(III) with Salen type Schiff base ligand via [3+2] cycloaddition reaction of metal coordinated

azide with a cyanopyridine. Interestingly, the pyridine group is lost during the formation of the tetrazole. The facile synthesis of complex **1** would, therefore, afford a convenient synthetic route for this type of tetrazole Schiff base complexes of cobalt(III).

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Supplementary material

CCDC 874128 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for compound **1**. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

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- The ligand H₂L was synthesized by condensation of ethylenediamine with salicylaldehyde in dry methanol following the literature method. It was then used directly for the preparation of complexes without further purification. The ligand was then refluxed with a mixture of cobalt(II) acetate and sodium azide to prepare the desired oxo-bridged dimeric cobalt(III) compound [Co(L)(N₃)₂]₂²¹. A methanol solution (10 ml) of 2-cyanopyridine (110 mg, 1 mmol) was added to the methanol solution (10 ml) of the compound [Co(L)(N₃)₂] (1 mmol), under stirring condition and stirred for 2 h. Single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction analysis of **1** were obtained on overnight standing in fridge. Yield : 180 mg (41.16%). Anal. Calcd. (%) for C₁₇H₁₆CoN₉O₂ (437.32) : C, 46.69; H, 3.69; N, 28.83. Found : C, 46.7; H, 3.7; N, 28.9; UV/Vis (DMF) : λ_{max}(nm) (ε_{max}, dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) = 388 (649). Magnetic moment : diamagnetic. All the starting materials were commercially available, reagent grade, and used as purchased without further purification.
- Single crystals having suitable dimensions were used for data collection by means of a 'Bruker SMART APEX II' diffractometer equipped with graphite-monochromated Mo-Kα radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å) at 293 K. The structure was solved by direct methods and refined by full-matrix least squares on F², using the SHELX-97 package³⁶. Non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. The H atoms of the water molecule of crystallization and that of ammonium ion were located by difference Fourier maps and were kept at fixed positions. Other hydrogen atoms were placed in their geometrically idealized positions and constrained to ride on the atoms to which they are attached. Empirical absorption corrections were carried out with the ABSPACK program³⁷. The structure was refined to R1 = 0.0875 and wR2 = 0.2085, for 3428 reflections with I > 2σ(I). Crystal data for **1** : Formula C₁₇H₁₆CoN₉O₂, Formula weight 437.32, Crystal system triclinic, Space group P-1, a (Å) = 246.301433(18), b (Å) = 6.3215(4), c (Å) = 19.8094(12), α = 90°, β = 90.393(4)°, γ = 90°, Z = 8, d_{calcd.} 247 (g cm⁻³) = 1.539, F(000) = 1792, Total reflections 28141, Unique reflections 4359, Observed data [I > 2σ(I)] 3428, R1 = 0.0875, wR2 = 0.2085.
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34. Hirshfeld surfaces³⁸⁻⁴⁰ and the associated 2D-fingerprint⁴¹⁻⁴³ plots were calculated using Crystal Explorer⁴⁴, which accepted a structure input file in CIF format. Bond lengths to hydrogen atoms were set to standard values. For each point on the Hirshfeld isosurface, two distances d_e , the distance from the point to the nearest nucleus external to the surface and d_i , the distance to the nearest nucleus internal to the surface, were defined. The normalized contact distance (d_{norm}) based on d_e and d_i was given by

$$d_{\text{norm}} = \frac{(d_i - r_i^{\text{vdW}})}{r_i^{\text{vdW}}} + \frac{(d_e - r_e^{\text{vdW}})}{r_e^{\text{vdW}}}$$
 where r_i^{vdW} and r_e^{vdW} are the van der Waals radii of the atoms. The value of d_{norm} was negative or positive depending on intermolecular contacts being shorter or longer than the van der Waals separations. The parameter d_{norm} displayed a surface with a red-white-blue color scheme, where bright red spots highlighted shorter contacts, white areas represented contacts around the van der Waals separation, and blue regions were devoid of close contacts. For a given crystal structure and set of spherical atomic electron densities,
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